

اتجاهات العاملين بالقطاع السياحي نحو المعالجة الإعلامية لتحديات التنمية السياحية المستدامة
دراسة تطبيقية على إذاعة الإسكندرية

**Attitudes Of Workers in Tourism Sector Towards Media Treatment of Sustainable Tourism
Development Challenges,**

An Applied Study on Alexandria Radio

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Abstract:

This study deals with the challenges of sustainable tourism development in the Alexandria Governorate and knowing the extent to which workers in the tourism sector rely on radio as a source of information presented on the radio.

The objectives of the study are numerous. The most important of which is identifying the most important challenges facing sustainable tourism development in Alexandria Governorate, and identifying the extent to which workers in the tourism sector (governmental and private) in the region of Alexandria depend on Alexandria Radio in their knowledge of the challenges of sustainable tourism development, while identifying methods for media treatment of the challenges facing sustainable tourism development on Alexandria Radio from the perspective of workers tourism sector.

Among the questions raised by the study are: What are the most prominent challenges facing sustainable tourism development in the region? How effective is the radio in playing an educational role for the target audience? What is the listening rate and follow-up periods for the appropriate Alexandria Radio? It relied on the analytical descriptive method, using the survey method, and the researcher used the questionnaire as a tool for collecting data.

Among the most important findings of the study are: The most important challenges facing sustainable tourism development in Alexandria are traffic congestion, and the problem of garbage. In Al Beheira region, the increase in tourism activity was represented in the summer, which leads to higher prices and tourism services.

However, media treatment of the challenges relied on highlighting important development issues and alerting to environmental dangers within the community.

Key Words: radio; challenges; sustainable tourism development; development issues; environmental hazards.

The Problem of the Study:

Identifying the challenges of sustainable tourism development in the Region of Alexandria, and finding out the extent to which workers in the tourism sector depend on radio as a source of information.

The Importance of the Study:

Knowing the challenges facing sustainable tourism development plans and learning about the trends of workers in the tourism sector (government and private) in order to increase the effectiveness of the media message provided by (radio).

The Objectives of the Study:

- 1- Identify the most important challenges facing sustainable tourism development in the region of Alexandria.
- 2- Identify the extent to which workers in the tourism sector (government and private) in Alexandria region rely on (Radio Alexandria) in their knowledge of the challenges of sustainable tourism development .
- 3- How media treats the challenges facing sustainable tourism development by Alexandria Radio from the perspective of workers in the tourism sector.

The Study Questions :

- 1- What are the main challenges facing sustainable tourism development in the region?
- 2- How effective (radio) is in playing the awareness role of the target audience?
- 3- What is the rate of listening and follow-up periods of the appropriate Radio Alexandria?
- 4- What are the proposals to activate the role of Alexandria Radio development?

Theoretical guidelines: The theory of dependence on the media .

Keywords: Radio, Challenges, Sustainable Tourism Development .

Methodological research procedures :

Type of study: The descriptive studies.

The methodology: the descriptive analytical method used in this survey method and the researcher relied on the questionnaire form to collect data,

The Most Important Findings of the Study :

- 1- The challenges in **Alexandria Governorate are:** traffic congestion, and the problem of garbage .
- 2- **Beheira Governorate:** dredging and construction of agricultural land, poor road network and traffic accidents .
- 3- **Matrouh Governorate:** Increased tourism activity (summer) leading to higher prices and tourism services .
- 4- While media treatment of the challenges is to highlight important development issues and alert to environmental hazards within the community .
- 5- The proposals of workers in the tourism sector are to increase the participation of specialists because of their ability to convince more, increase the interest of development media programs and materials, and display tourist materials in periods with higher listening rates.

الملخص:

تتناول هذه الدراسة تحديات التنمية السياحية المستدامة في إقليم الإسكندرية، ومعرفة مدى اعتماد العاملين بالقطاع السياحي على الإذاعة كمصدر للمعلومات، وتمثلت أهمية الدراسة في معرفة التحديات التي تواجه خطط التنمية السياحية المستدامة والتعرف على اتجاهات العاملين بالقطاع السياحي (الحكومي والخاص) من أجل زيادة فاعلية الرسالة الإعلامية المقدمة عبر الإذاعة.

وتعددت أهداف الدراسة ومن أهمها تحديد أهم التحديات التي تواجه التنمية السياحية المستدامة بإقليم الإسكندرية، والتعرف على مدى اعتماد العاملين بالقطاع السياحي (الحكومي والخاص) بإقليم الإسكندرية على إذاعة الإسكندرية في معرفتهم بتحديات التنمية السياحية المستدامة مع تحديد طرق المعالجة الإعلامية للتحديات التي تواجه التنمية السياحية المستدامة بإذاعة الإسكندرية من منظور العاملين بالقطاع السياحي.

ومن التساؤلات التي طرحتها الدراسة، ما أبرز التحديات التي تواجه التنمية السياحية المستدامة بالإقليم؟ وما مدى فاعلية الإذاعة في القيام بالدور التوعوي للجمهور المستهدف؟ وما هو معدل الاستماع وفترات المتابعة لإذاعة الإسكندرية المناسبة؟ واعتمدت الدراسة على فروض نظرية الاعتماد على وسائل الإعلام، وتعد من الدراسات الوصفية حيث اعتمدت على المنهج الوصفي التحليلي مستخدمة في ذلك طريقة المسح واستخدمت الباحثة استمارة الاستبيان كأداة لجمع البيانات.

ومن أهم النتائج التي توصلت إليها الدراسة: أن أهم التحديات التي تواجه التنمية السياحية المستدامة في الإسكندرية في الازدحام والتكدس المروري، ومشكلة القمامة، وفي محافظة البحيرة تمثلت في تجريف الأراضي الزراعية، والبناء عليها، ضعف شبكة الطرق وحوادث السير، أما تحديات التنمية المستدامة في محافظة مطروح تمثلت زيادة النشاط السياحي صيفا مما يؤدي إلى ارتفاع الأسعار والخدمات السياحية.

في حين اعتمدت المعالجة الإعلامية للتحديات في تسليط الضوء على قضايا تنموية مهمة، والتنبيه لأخطار بيئية، داخل المجتمع.

الكلمات المفتاحية: الإذاعة؛ التحديات؛ التنمية السياحية المستدامة؛ قضايا تنموية؛ أخطار البيئة.

مشكلة الدراسة:

التعرف على تحديات التنمية السياحية المستدامة في إقليم الإسكندرية، ومعرفة مدى اعتماد العاملين بالقطاع السياحي على الإذاعة كمصدر للمعلومات.

أهمية الدراسة:

معرفة التحديات التي تواجه خطط التنمية السياحية المستدامة والتعرف على اتجاهات العاملين بالقطاع السياحي (الحكومي والخاص) من أجل زيادة فاعلية الرسالة الإعلامية المقدمة عبر الإذاعة.

أهداف الدراسة:

- 1- تحديد أهم التحديات التي تواجه التنمية السياحية المستدامة بإقليم الإسكندرية.
- 2- التعرف على مدى اعتماد العاملين بالقطاع السياحي -الحكومي والخاص- بإقليم الإسكندرية على إذاعة الإسكندرية في معرفتهم بتحديات التنمية السياحية المستدامة.
- 3- كيفية المعالجة الإعلامية للتحديات التي تواجه التنمية السياحية المستدامة بإذاعة الإسكندرية من منظور العاملين بالقطاع السياحي.

تساؤلات الدراسة:

1- ما أبرز التحديات التي تواجه التنمية السياحية المستدامة بالإسكندرية؟

2- مدى فاعلية الإذاعة في القيام بالدور التوعوي للجمهور المستهدف؟

3- ما هو معدل الاستماع وفترات المتابعة لإذاعة الإسكندرية المناسبة؟

4- ما هي مقترحات تفعيل دور إذاعة الإسكندرية تنموياً؟

الموجهات النظرية: فروض نظرية الاعتماد على وسائل الإعلام.

الكلمات المفتاحية: الإذاعة، التحديات، التنمية السياحية المستدامة.

الإجراءات المنهجية للبحث:

نوع الدراسة: من الدراسات الوصفية.

منهج الدراسة: المنهج الوصفي التحليلي مستخدمة في ذلك طريقة المسح، واعتمدت الباحثة على استمارة الإستبيان كأداة

لجمع البيانات.

أهم نتائج الدراسة:

1- تمثلت التحديات في الإسكندرية في الازدحام والتكدس المروري، ومشكلة القمامة.

2- البحيرة: تجريف الأراضي الزراعية، والبناء عليها، ضعف شبكة الطرق وحوادث السير.

3- مطروح: زيادة النشاط السياحي صيفاً مما يؤدي إلى ارتفاع الأسعار والخدمات السياحية.

في حين تمثلت المعالجة الإعلامية للتحديات في تسليط الضوء على قضايا تنموية مهمة، والتنبيه لأخطار بيئية داخل

المجتمع.

وتمثلت مقترحات العاملين في القطاع السياحي في زيادة مشاركة المتخصصين لقدرتهم على الإقناع أكثر، وزيادة

اهتمام البرامج والمواد الإعلامية التنموية، وعرض المواد السياحية في الفترات التي تحظى بمعدلات استماع أعلى.

Introduction:

Sustainable tourism has become an approach and a method on which many international tourism institutions are based, Contrary to what many people believe, the application of the concept of sustainable tourism is not financially costly, and may pose a threat to increasing opportunities for sustainable tourism development.

Based on the foregoing, the researcher studied the challenges and obstacles facing sustainable tourism development in the Alexandria region. In order to confront it, reveal it, and find out the effectiveness of radio in influencing the attitudes of workers in the tourism sector, and to find out how the media addresses the challenges facing sustainable tourism development in Alexandria Radio from the perspective of workers in the tourism sector(public and private) in the Alexandria region and the challenges that impede sustainable tourism development in the governorates of Alexandria, Beheira and Matrouh through the following elements:

The Problem of the Study:

Given the importance of the role of media, especially radio (audio-visual) in development in its various forms, as its role is to address the issues of the local community and the challenges and difficulties facing it and impede the implementation of its development plans, the researcher found that identifying the obstacles and challenges facing sustainable tourism development in the Alexandria region puts it in the hands of those responsible for development plans in the region, which helps determine how to face these challenges, in

addition to the importance of knowing the extent to which workers in the tourism sector depend on radio as a source of information in order to increase the effectiveness of media message presented through the local media, especially (audio broadcasting) and its impact on the attitudes and knowledge of the target audience. Accordingly the researcher formulated the study problem as follows:

Attitudes of Workers in Tourism Sector towards Media Treatment of the Challenges of Sustainable Tourism Development

An Applied Study on Alexandria Radio

The Importance of the Study:

The importance of the study is divided into theoretical importance and practical importance, which can be dealt with as follows:

Theoretical Importance:

- 1- The importance of this study stems from the importance of the issue it addresses, as it deals with the issue of sustainable tourism development, and the most important obstacles it faces in the Alexandria region, which may affect development plans and projects in the provinces of the region.
- 2- Through the researcher's review of many previous studies, the researcher found that the previous studies did not address the link between the challenges of sustainable tourism development and the role of local radio in defining these challenges and influencing the knowledge of the target audience. Previous studies dealt with it.

The Applied Importance:

- 1- Activating the role of local radio in dealing with issues of sustainable tourism development by identifying the most important challenges in the region in order to facilitate their treatment in media and assisting workers in tourism sector in employing the results of the study in their field.
- 2- The study benefits those in charge of tourism development plans in the Egyptian society to identify the obstacles facing sustainable tourism development in the Alexandria region and its three governorates, with the aim of correcting the path aimed at heading towards the element of sustainability in tourism development according to Egypt's vision and 2030 strategy, **The Objectives of the Study**

The objectives of the study are defined in several main axes that can be addressed as follows:

- 1- Identifying the most important challenges facing sustainable tourism development in the Alexandria region.
- 2- Identify the extent to which workers in the tourism sector (governmental and private) in the Alexandria region depend on the local media (Alexandria Radio) in their knowledge of the challenges of sustainable tourism development in the Alexandria region, and the extent to which they benefit from media coverage of these challenges.
- 3- Standing on how the media addresses the challenges facing sustainable tourism development in Alexandria Radio from the perspective of workers in the tourism sector.

The Study Questions:

- 1- What are the most prominent challenges facing sustainable tourism development in the Alexandria region and its three governorates? Through this main question, the researcher raised a set of sub-questions, which are:

- 2- Is there a difference in the forms of challenges facing sustainable tourism development in the governorates of Alexandria?
- 3- Measuring the effectiveness of (radio) in carrying out media and awareness role for the target audience on issues related to sustainable tourism development and its challenges in the study area.
- 4- What is the listening rate and follow-up periods for Alexandria Radio suitable for workers in the tourism sector?
- 5- What are the proposals of workers in the tourism sector to activate the role of Alexandria Radio in serving sustainable tourism development issues?

The Theoretical Guidelines for the Study:

A- Theoretical Framework:

1- The Concept of Theory Mass Media Dependency Theory:

Prepare one of the environmental theories, which look at society as an organic structure. Media has influence direct strong, and sometimes other indirect and rather weak effects (Rokeach, Sandra J.Ball, 1998) may be the concept of dependence means the communicative behavior of the respondents, specifically the type of the medium, the rate of its use, the type of programs and topics that he is keen on, and his confidence in it. It may also mean the degree of considering the communicative medium as the primary source of information, as the level of dependence of the individual on the medium is his conscious and rational decision of its importance to him as a source of his information. and his preference for it. (Ronald J.Faber, Stephen D.Reese, and H.Leslie Stee, 1985).

From the basic role played by the media and communication in social relations, the founders of the theory of dependence (Rokeach, Sandra J.Ball, 1998) saw that there is a mutual dependence between mass media and the social system in which it arises, Therefore, the use of media by individuals is not done in isolation from the influence of society, and that the ability of the media to influence increases when these means carry out the function of transmitting information intensively and continuously (Abdel-Hamid, 2015).

As to holding the social structure leads to weakening the interaction between individuals and society, and thus may make the media an alternative to this interaction so that the individual becomes more dependent on the media to obtain information, and an active and vital element in communication process. The founders of the theory believe that the media has a relationship with individuals and societies, and this may be the relationship is variable or regular, strong or weak. Theory stipulates two basic conditions for the occurrence of this interaction and the formation of a relationship of mutual dependence between the public and the media, which are: (Abdel-Hamid, 2015).

- 1- If media has achieved important functions in society, and it is able to satisfy the needs of the public, this will increase its dependence on it.
- 2- If the intensity of conflicts is high in society, this will affect the intensity of public dependence on media.

The theory seeks to focus on the relationships between systems and their components, as it looks at society from the perspective of the power of media in its control over the sources of information that individuals and social systems depend on to achieve their goals. (Hassan Emad Makkawi, Laila Hussein Al-Sayed, 2016).

2- Pillars of Relationships Reliance on the Media is Based on:

- A. Objectives:** Members of the public rely on the media to achieve the following goals: comprehension guidance – entertainment.

- B. Sources:** The ability of media to influence the audience increases when the information continues to be transmitted intensively, and the power of the media lies in its control over the sources of information and it obliges individuals to achieve their personal goals, and in order to meet their knowledge needs about the world and the society surrounding them.

3- Assumptions of the Theory of Dependence on Media:

- A. It is considered that media system is important to society, as the degree of reliance on it to satisfy the needs of the public increases, and it decreases in the presence of alternative channels of information. The public also differs in the degree of its dependence on the media as a result of their differences in goals, interests and individual needs. (Rokeach, Sandra J.Ball, 1998).
- B. The use of mass media and their impact does not occur in isolation from the effects of the social system to which the public and the media belong. (Melvin. L. Devler and Sandra Paul Rokic, 2004).
- C. Cases of instability that occur in the social system increase the public's need for information, and thus increase its dependence on the media to satisfy this need. (Pablo Hallpern, 1999).
- D. The public's dependence on media increases whenever media system is able to respond to the needs of the social system and the public. (Rokeach, Sandra J.Ball, 1998).
- E. The extent to which individuals depend on media is affected by several variables. The most important of which is the nature of media in society, the extent of its diversity and the content it provides, in addition to the factors specific to society itself.

4- Aspects of Benefit from the Theory in the Current Study:

The theory of dependence on the media is an entry point that determines the public's relationship with media, as the attitudes of individuals towards issues are affected by their dependence on media, which affects their behavior as well. The degree of public dependence on media to obtain information is the basis for understanding the impact of media messages on feelings, behavior and attitudes. It helps in understanding the relationship between media and the public, and focuses on this in answering the question: Why does audience of workers in tourism sector in the Alexandria region follow the local radio (Alexandria Radio)? To achieve the goal, which is to identify the challenges of sustainable tourism development, it is possible to understand the interactive relationship between media and the public as one is indispensable for the other.

B- Basic Concepts:

1- Radio:

Procedurally determined by the researcher: that it is the (audio) radio that serves a limited society, belongs to it, and is concerned with its problems and issues, it is the radio station that is heard in the city of Alexandria, that is, Alexandria Radio, which was established in (1954)

2- Challenges:

They are problems or obstacles of various and overlapping dimensions (political - economic - social - cultural) stemming from the local, regional or external environment and may pose a threat to the future of sustainable tourism development in the study area. The challenge is every action that impedes development in the country.

3- Sustainable Tourism Development:

They are the various development plans and programs that seek to achieve a continuous and balanced increase in tourism and environmental resources and aim to achieve the largest possible rate of tourism growth, while ensuring that future generations benefit.

Previous Studies:

The researcher conducted a survey on some studies related to the topic of the current research (Arabic and foreign), the most important of which are presented as follows:

The First Axis: Previous Studies that dealt with the role of radio in the development of the local community and Sustainable development.

The Second Axis: Previous studies concerned with sustainable tourism development and its challenges.

The Third Axis: Previous studies that dealt with the role of radio in the development of the local community and sustainable development

1- **Study each of Hunaida Qandil Abu Bakr, Yasser Youssef,** (Huneida Qandeel Abu Bakr, 2017), Centered Study problem in calendar Radio role in instilling the values of sustainable development in the Arab region by focusing on analysis programs developmental broadcasting, which is broadcast by Abu Dhabi Radio (a model), and the importance it attaches to development programs, adopted. This study is based on the quantitative and qualitative analysis of the content of development programs in Arab radio stations, taking Abu Dhabi Radio as an applied sample for these radio stations, which specializes in the concept of sustainable development. Loop, it is the main outcome in the study analysis:

Pain development issue is note with interest adequate in terms of time assigned for development programmes.

B-I lack topic development to focus on a specific development issue, which indicates the lack of a strategic plan to address the issue of sustainable development, and prioritize it according to the need for it.

C- Revealing the study analysis not allocating channels or programs to deal with development issues in general.

2- **Study both Iman Al-Alami and Abboud Zarqin** (Iman Al-Alami and Abboud Zarqin, 2016), the study is what are the solutions for the sustainability of this resource and achieving continuous growth in it? Media also plays a positive role in helping to achieve sustainable development plans and goals.

3- **The study of Saudi Al-Hassan, Al-Hassan Andani and Abdullah Abdul-Malik,** (Al-hassan, Seidu, Alhassan Andani, and Abdulai Abdul-Malik, 2011), the study sought to identify the role of community radio in improving livelihoods, a case study of Simli Radio in Ghana, and an analysis of the challenges facing Simli Radio. The study used the interview and observation guide as a tool for data collection, and the study included (518) communities in two regions, and the results reached the following: Simli Radio worked to improve awareness and knowledge of solutions to the problems of community development in various sectors.

The study showed that the listeners depend on information related to development in various sectors in other societies through Simli Radio. It also indicated that there are several challenges facing Simli Radio, including: Its absence negatively affected the provision of services and management of the radio, in addition to the disappearance of radio programs, despite their importance to the listener, after the presenters of the program left the country, and this is a result of the mistake of building programs around one individual only.

- 4- **Study by Noha Abdel Maqsood Ghaly** (Ghaly, 2008), targeted studying the role played by Alexandria Radio and Television in presenting the problems of the local community and addressing them, through two studies: exploratory and field. Among the mass programs and news bulletins presented by both local radio and television. Among the most important results of the analytical study are: It showed that the volume of interest in covering the news of Alexandrian society by the Alexandria Radio bulletin is greater than the volume of interest in the news bulletin of Channel 5, as indicated by the means of support used in the news bulletin in both Alexandria Radio And Channel 5 indicates the continued superiority of Alexandria Radio, as it relies mainly on two types: reports and recorded external interviews.
- 5- **The study of Ibrahim Saeed Abdul Karim** (Karim, 2006), the study dealt with the role of regional media in addressing local environmental issues. An analytical study on Central Delta Radio and Channel Six, the field study was conducted on a sample of the radio's target audience, in Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate, the researcher conducted an analytical study and used the survey method and the correlation studies method and relied on the content analysis to choose a random sample. A regular stratified sample of 400 members of the target audience of the audio-visual radio station in the center of the Delta in Kafr El-Sheikh governorate was drawn regularly, and the study found several results, the most important of which are:

The Second Axis: Previous studies concerned with sustainable tourism development and its challenges.

- 1- **Lourdes Ruiz Study** (Ruiz, 2017), the study aimed to identify the negative environmental effects of tourism on local communities in the Ecuadorian highlands region, and the effects being studied were classified into effects on the physical, biological, social, cultural and economic environment. The most important findings of the study are:
 - a. The components of the harmful effects of the environment occurred due to excessive exploitation.
 - b. The study stated that the economic effects of tourism are positive in view of the increase in employment opportunities, but there is insufficient perception of the cumulative effects of tourism and the proposed measures and existing monitoring efforts are generally weak among tourism companies on the one hand and municipal governments and public institutions on the other.
 - c. These measures were not accompanied by a solid environmental culture that seeks to preserve the nature and cultural identity of the local population.
- 2- **The study of Abeer Mahmoud Abdel Hakim**, (Hakim, 2016), the problem of the study revolves around identifying the basic features of ecotourism and its role in achieving sustainable tourism development, as well as identifying the means by which ecotourism can be developed in Egypt in order to shift to green tourism. The study concluded several results, including: Ecotourism in Egypt faces many challenges, the most important of which identifying tourist places and working to construct and support the infrastructure and support services in accordance with all environmental considerations, with the lack of environmental awareness for all segments of society through all print, audio and visual media.
- 3- **A study by Gholamreza Janbaz Ghobadi and Mahin Shah Verdian** (Ghobadi, Gholam reza Janbaz, and Verdian, Mahin Shah, 2016), it dealt with the identification of the environmental effects of tourism development in (Nowshahr city) the impact of tourism on the environment of this city, and the analysis of the relationship between environmental tourism and sustainability. Sustainable urban development is based on a conceptual model, aspects and indicators of sustainable urban development are analyzed . It combines

three main elements of development which are (Society, Economy and the Environment), It is an applied and descriptive study. It used a questionnaire on (380) heads of families from the local population who were included in the research sample. (384) tourists were included. Among the most important results of the study: There is a significant relationship between environmental impacts and tourism development in (Nowshahr) in terms of the impact of Tourism development is based on increasing the use of natural resources, increasing construction and destroying natural resources, and development from construction without management and planning.

There is a great relationship between tourism development and its environmental impact in (Nowshahr) in terms of the lack of basic facilities for every tourist (toilets, restaurants, and parking lots). The prosperity of tourism in every geographical area is linked to air, water, sound pollution, waste accumulation, and environmental pollution.

4- The study of Yasser Awad Abdel Rasoul, (Abdel-Rasoul, 2016), the study aimed to clarify the concepts of the main obstacles to sustainable tourism development and the most important obstacles it faces, and the economic effects. The study ended with identifying the most important obstacles facing sustainable tourism development, including economic problems. Egyptians of all categories are influential in tourist attraction, as it is one of the tourism obstacles, as they deal with them as a matter of material exploitation and also the problem of street vendors from the problems that affect tourism and contribute to giving a bad image of Egypt.

The problem is on tourism, as the study confirmed that a large percentage of tourists unanimously agreed that they were subjected to harassment by street vendors, special obstacles to neglecting archaeological tourist areas and surrounding facilities, and other obstacles related to pollution in the Nile waters and beaches, and obstacles related to tourism management. responsible and others related to economic, financial and customs policy, and obstacles related to tourism work, as workers in the tourism sector confirmed that the workers are not trained in a way that qualifies them for direct contact.

5- A study of each Muhammad Ibrahim Iraqi and Farouk Abd al-Nabi Atalla) (Muhammad Ibrahim Iraqi, Farouk Abd al-Nabi Atallah, 2007), the study aimed to define the concept of sustainable tourism development, and to clarify the difference between traditional tourism development and sustainable tourism development, and identified its principles and objectives. In tourism development, namely: the extent of applying the principles of sustainable tourism development related to the infrastructure in hotels in Alexandria, hotels and tourist resorts, where the study reached several results.

The most important of which are: that there are a set of obstacles towards the application of sustainability in the basic elements of the environment, including: the lack of established plans in hotels to benefit from the elements of the basic environment and complementary services; which achieves the financial benefit for it, while preserving the environment at the same time and the high cost of purchasing and managing environmentally friendly clean technology, such as the exploitation of solar energy by using solar cells.

Commenting on Previous Studies:

Points of agreement:

- 1- The current study agreed with previous studies in dealing with the local audio media, in particular Alexandria Radio, as in the study (Ghaly, 2008).

- 2- The current study agreed with previous studies in its use of the survey method, and the questionnaire form as a tool for data collection, as in the study of (Ghaly, 2008) - (Karim, 2006)
- 3- The current study also agreed with previous studies in addressing the challenges of sustainable tourism development in general, as in the study (Ruiz, 2017), and the features of eco-tourism, as in the study (Hakim, 2016), the challenges of sustainable tourism development, especially in Alexandria, as in the study of (Muhammad Ibrahim Iraqi, Farouk Abd al-Nabi Atallah, 2007).

The Differences:

- 1- Previous studies did not address the challenges facing sustainable tourism development in the governorates of Alexandria, especially the governorates of Beheira and Matrouh.
- 2- None of the previous studies dealt with the role of radio in addressing the challenges of sustainable tourism development in the governorates of the region.

Benefit from Previous Studies

- 1- The researcher benefited from previous studies in formulating her research problem, defining its objectives, choosing the method and data collection tools.
- 2- The researcher determined the study sample through which good results of the study can be reached.

The Research Methodological Procedures:

1- The Type of Study and its Method: This study belongs to descriptive studies. The study relied on the descriptive analytical method, using the survey method, which is defined as one of the methods related to collecting information.

2- Study Population and Sample and Data Collection Tools:

A- The Human Frame: Workers in the tourism sector (governmental and private) who are present in the governorates of the region. The sample (508 respondents) included (308 males) and (200 females).

B- Geographical framework: The region of Alexandria Governorate, which includes the governorates of (Alexandria - Beheira - Matrouh).

C- Study Tool:

The researcher used the questionnaire form to collect information, the form was arbitrated, and the researcher made the modifications.

The questionnaire was prepared in its initial form and presented to a group of (8) arbitrators, and the required modifications were made by the arbitrators.

Then the researcher conducted an experimental test on a number of (30) respondents, and this test provided an opportunity to clarify some basic points related to the form, such as an amendment to some vague questions, deleting some questions and replacing them with more clear questions, and thus the questionnaire was modified in its final form, ready for application.

The questionnaire contained (10) questions and used more than (4) various measures. Some questions have been reformulated and the questionnaire has been applied workers in the public and private tourism sectors

Data Analysis and Statistical Methods Used in the Study:

Data analysis was done using the statistical analysis program "Statistical Packages for Social Sciences Statistical package for social sciences ".SPPSS" (V.25)

The following statistical methods have been used:

- 1- Frequencies and relative frequencies.

2- Analysis of multiple responses.

The Difficulties that Tht Researcher Encountered while Applying the Questionnaire were as Follows:

1- Non-cooperation of workers in the (private) tourism sector in answering the questionnaire because they are not familiar with the concept of the questionnaire; this required an explanation of the concept and content of the question and the purpose of its implementation.

While the researcher found cooperation between the government sector workers in answering the questionnaire, but many of the forms were lost by some, which required printing other questionnaire forms, and going to the place of work of the sample members more than once.

2- The non-cooperation of some private entities and institutions in participating in answering the questionnaire, such as the Tourist Guides Syndicate, the Federation of Chambers of Tourist Companies, and the Federation of Hotel Rooms; for fear of giving any information related to their work, as they found that this questionnaire and its content contradict the nature of their work.

While the researcher found great cooperation on the part of the Syndicate of Tourism and Hotels Workers in Alexandria, the Office of the Ministry of Tourism in Alexandria and the Authority. Regional to stimulate tourism in the province Alexandria.

The Analysis of the Field Study on Workers in Tourism Sector

Schedule (1)

Explains the description of the study sample of workers in the tourism sector

%	K	Demographic variables	
60.6%	308	Male	Type
39.4%	200	Feminine	
8.5%	43	Less from 30	Age group
23.6%	120	30 lessfrom35	
21.5%	109	35 less from 40	
16.3%	83	40 less from45	
30.1%	153	From 45 and over	
48.4%	246	private sector	The Tourism Sector In Which It Operates
51.6%	262	government sector	
15.4%	78	Boss	Type of job in the tourism sector
2.6%	13	Tourism expert	
5.5%	28	government official	
47.6%	242	Employee	
7.9%	40	A tour guide	
21.1%	107	Other	Professional Experience
11.6%	59	Less than 5 years	
28.9%	147	5 less out of 10	
19.9%	101	10 less from 15	
17.3%	88	15 less from 20	

22.2%	113	20 years and over	Place of residence
60.6%	308	Alexandria Governorate	
20.7%	105	Beheira Governorate	
18.7%	95	Matrouh Governorate	
100%	508	Total	

Schedule (2)

Shows the extent of listening to Radio Alexandria

%	K	Extent of Listening
23.8%	121	No
29.5%	150	Yes
46.7%	237	Sometimes
100%	508	Total

From the previous table, it is clear that less than half of the respondents working in the tourism sector (governmental and private) sometimes follow Radio Alexandria.

Schedule (3)

Explains the relationship between listening to Alexandria Radio and the nature of the tourism sector

Total		Government Sector		Private Sector		The Nature of the Business Sector Tourist Listen to the Radio
%	K	%	K	%	K	
23.8%	121	23.3%	61	24.4%	60	No
29.5%	150	26.7%	70	32.5%	80	Yes
46.7%	237	50%	131	43.1%	106	Sometimes
100%	508	100%	262	100%	246	Total

From the previous table, we can note that less than half of the respondents working in the tourism sector (governmental and private) sometimes follow Radio Alexandria. While less than a third of the respondents follow Radio Alexandria. The rate of listening to Alexandria Radio is higher among workers in the private tourism sector than in the government sector.

Schedule (4)

**Shows the Periods During which Workers in t Tourism Sector Follow the Programs Presented By Radio
Alexandria**

%	K	Time Period
25.8%	131	Morning Period before 12 Noon
5.1%	26	Noon Period between 12 pm - 5 pm
34.4%	174	The Evening Period Is Between 5 pm - 10 pm
34.8%	177	Evening Period after 10 pm
100%	508	Total

From the previous table, we can see that most of the following periods in which the sample members are workers in tourism sector (governmental and private), the programs presented via Alexandria Radio are the evening period between 5 pm - 10 pm, and the evening period after 10 pm

Schedule (5)

**Adoption of workers in the tourism sector on Alexandria Radio as the main source of information on
Challenges of sustainable tourism development**

Total		Government Sector		Private Sector		Nature of the Business Sector Tourist Accreditation Radio Alexandria
%	K	%	K	%	K	
23.8%	121	22.5%	59	25.2%	62	To a Great Extent
43.7%	222	44.7%	117	42.7%	105	Moderately
32.5%	165	32.8%	86	32.1%	79	To a Small Degree
100%	508	100%	262	100%	246	Total

From the previous table, we can note that workers in the private tourism sector depend on the local media as a main source for the challenges of sustainable development in the Alexandria region, more than workers in the government sector, and less than half of the sample depends on average on the local media as a main source for the challenges of sustainable development in the region Alexandria.

Schedule (6)

Explains Aspects of Benefiting from Following (Radio Alexandria)

Proportion of the Sample	Responses		Aspects of Benefiting from the Follow-up to Alexandria Radio
	%	K	
68.1%	28.1%	233	1- Knowledge of Environmental Tourism Issues and Sustainable Tourism Development in Alexandria Region in General and my Governorates in Particular.
48.8%	20.1%	167	2 - Knowledge of the Challenges Facing Sustainable Tourism Development.
50%	20.6%	171	3- Knowledge of Laws and Legislations Related to Increasing Rates of Sustainable Tourism Development and Preserving the Environment.
59.4%	24.5	203	4- Knowing the Efforts of the State and Various Institutions in the Field of Sustainable Tourism Development and the Environment.
242.7%	100%	830	Total

From the previous table, it is clear that the aspects of benefit were represented in: knowledge of environmental tourism issues and sustainable tourism development in the Alexandria region in general and my governorate in particular, knowledge of the efforts of the state and various institutions in the field of sustainable tourism development and the environment, knowledge of laws and legislations related to increasing development rates, Sustainable tourism and environmental preservation Knowledge of the challenges facing sustainable tourism development.

Schedule (7)

Explains the Reasons for not Benefiting from the Follow-up of Tourism and Environmental Programmes. Alexandria Radio

Proportion of T=the Sample	Responses		Reasons For Not Using
	%	K	
8.7%	4.3%	18	1- Using Vague Scientific Terms without Explaining hem.
31.3%	15.7%	65	2- Do not Provide Illustrative forms and Examples of the Tourist and Environmental Information that you Provide.
31.3%	15.7%	66	3- It Deals with Environmental Tourism Issues in an Ideal Manner that is Difficult to Apply Realistically.
	22.9%	95	4- It Lacks Immediacy, and is Very Late in Addressing the

45.7%			Challenges of Sustainable Tourism Development and Does not Address them in a Timely Manner.
54.8%	27.5%	114	5- Do not Present in an Attractive Manner.
26.9%	13.5%	56	6- Focus on some Aspects and Neglect Others.
199%	100%	414	Total

From the previous table, we can note that most of the reasons for not benefiting from follow-up tourism and environmental programs Alexandria Radio is due to the fact that it is not presented in an attractive manner, lacks immediacy, and is very late in addressing the challenges of sustainable tourism development and does not address them in a timely manner. It does not provide models and illustrative examples of the tourism and environmental information it provides.

Schedule (8)

Explains the (Alexandria Radio) Handling of the Challenges of Sustainable Tourism Development in the Alexandria Region

Proportion of the Sample		Responses	What (Alexandria Radio) to the Challenges of Sustainable Tourism Development
	%	K	
41.6%	24.2%	143	Presenting Programs Aimed at Identifying these Problems and Challenges
84.3%	49.2%	290	Hosting Specialists and Officials in the Field of Tourism.
34.9%	20.3%	120	Provide Solutions to these Challenges.
10.8%	6.3%	37	It has no Role in Sustainable Tourism Development.
171.5%	100%	590	Total

From the previous table, we can note that hosting specialists and officials in the field of tourism and presenting programs aimed at identifying these problems and challenges and providing solutions to those challenges was what (Alexandria Radio) dealt with most in its media treatment.

Schedule (9)

Explains some of the challenges facing sustainable tourism development in the governorates of Alexandria

Matrouh Governorate		Beheira Governorate		Alexandria Governorate		Challenges
Proportion of the Sample	Responses		Proportion of the Sample	Responses		
	%	K		%	K	

e									
22.0%	16.0 %	107	35.2%	25.5%	171	80.7%	58.5%	392	1 - Pollution of all Kinds
32.0%	22.2 %	153	40.6%	28.2%	194	71.5%	49.6%	342	2- Poor Road Network and Accidents
17.0%	13.8 %	80	21.3%	17.3%	100	84.7%	68.9%	398	3- Congestion and Traffic Congestion
38.2%	25.2 %	157	37.2%	24.6%	153	75.9%	50.2%	312	4- Conflict of Laws and Legislations Related to Tourism Work between Different Institutions and Bodies
43.8%	30.0 %	210	22.9%	15.7%	110	79.0%	54.2%	379	5- High Prices of Tourism and Hotel Goods and Services
45.4%	26.1 %	217	46.9%	27.0%	224	81.6%	46.9%	390	6- The Rise in the Prices of Gasoline and Petroleum Derivatives
23.3%	18.4 %	58	12.9%	10.1%	32	90.8%	71.5%	226	7- Challenges Related to Security and Terrorist Incidents
46.5%	33.1 %	204	5.9%	4.2%	26	88.2%	62.7%	387	8- High Prices for Entry to Beaches
29.2%	23.5 %	115	4.3%	3.5%	17	90.9%	73.1%	358	9- Unplanned Expansion of Hotel Establishments, and Filling in Parts of Beaches
17.1%	13.0 %	81	32.1%	24.4%	152	82.5%	62.7%	391	10 - The Problem of Garbage and its Spread
26.6%	18.8 %	111	41.5%	29.2%	173	73.9%	52.0%	308	11- Environmental Problems, for Example: The Transformation of Water Banks into the Sea or (the River) - Overfishing
36.5%	24.0 %	170	42.3%	27.8%	197	73.4%	48.2%	342	12- Poor Infrastructure

39.9%	28.2%	183	40.5%	28.7%	186	60.8%	43.1%	279	13- The Lack of Potable Water
19.1%	14.2%	85	39.5%	29.4%	176	75.6%	56.4%	337	14- Slums and Illegal Construction
50.2%	35.5%	237	18.4%	13.0%	87	72.7%	51.4%	343	15- The Seasonality of Tourism Work, and the Low Level of Training for Workers in the Tourism Sector
6.7%	5.5%	24	84.4%	69.1%	302	31.0%	25.4%	111	16- Bulldozing Agricultural Lands and Building on Them
42.2%	25.0%	35	30.1%	17.9%	25	96.4%	57.1%	80	17- Behaviors of Citizens with Tourists and their Financial Exploitation
51.3%	33.4%	231	37.1%	24.2%	167	65.1%	42.4%	293	18 - Distance from the Archaeological and Touristic Places to the Means of Transportation
39.8%	26.2%	187	39.1%	25.7%	184	73.2%	48.1%	344	19- Lack of Facilities and Services in Tourist Attractions
55.1%	37.3%	250	11.9%	8.1%	54	80.6%	54.6%	366	20- The Accumulation of Tourism Activity in Specific Periods (the Summer Season), Which Leads to an Increase in Prices and Tourism Services, and Sudden Pressure on Facilities.

We conclude from the table that there is a difference and diversity of challenges facing sustainable tourism development in the Alexandria region with its three governorates, depending on the geographical nature of each governorate.

Schedule (10)

Explains some proposals of workers in the tourism sector to activate the role of Alexandria Radio Serving sustainable tourism development issues

Proportion of the Sample	Responses	Proposals of Workers in the Tourism Sector to
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	%	K	Activate the Role of Radio Alexandria
33.6%	11.4%	169	1- Shedding light on successful models and experiences in the field of sustainable tourism development locally, regionally and internationally.
50.1%	17.1%	252	2- Simplifying information on sustainable tourism development through specialists.
30.4%	10.4%	153	3- Increasing public participation in media tourism contents.
43.9%	15.0%	221	4- The interest of programs and media materials in issues of sustainable environmental tourism development.
40.2%	13.7%	202	5- Displaying radio and television tourism materials during the periods that have the highest rates of listening and viewing.
41.7%	14.2%	210	6- Addressing the challenges facing local sustainable tourism development and providing solutions to them.
53.7%	18.3%	270	7- Increasing the participation of specialists in presenting issues of sustainable tourism development for their ability to convince more of the challenges and problems of tourism development.
293.6%	100%	1477	Total

From the previous table, we can note that the increased participation of specialists in presenting sustainable tourism development issues due to their ability to convince more of the challenges and problems of tourism development, in addition to addressing the challenges facing local sustainable tourism development and providing solutions to them, in addition to the interest of programs and media materials in tourism development issues. Sustainable environment, in addition to presenting radio and television tourism materials in periods that have higher listening and viewing rates, were the most proposals of workers in the tourism sector to activate the role of Alexandria Radio in serving sustainable.

The General Results of the Study:

The study concluded that the most prominent challenges facing sustainable tourism development in the Alexandria region, as identified by the sample members working in the tourism sector (public and private) in Alexandria, are as follows:

- 1- The behavior of citizens with tourists and their financial exploitation, the ill-conceived expansion of hotel facilities overlooking the beaches, filling parts of the sandy beach, challenges related to security and terrorist incidents, high prices for entering beaches, congestion, traffic congestion, the problem of garbage and its spread, high prices of gasoline and petroleum derivatives, pollution in addition to the accumulation

of tourism activity in specific periods (the summer season), which leads to higher prices and tourism services, pressure on facilities, and higher prices of tourism and hotel goods and services.

- 2- While the most prominent challenges facing sustainable tourism development in the Buheira Governorate were represented in: bulldozing agricultural land and building on it, high prices of gasoline and petroleum derivatives, and poor infrastructure, environmental problems, for example: the transformation of water drains into the sea or the river, overfishing, in addition to the weakness of the road network and the increase in accidents traffic and the lack of potable water in some areas, the spread of slums, illegal construction, the lack of facilities and services in tourist attractions, in addition to the conflict of laws and legislations related to tourism work between the various institutions and bodies, and the remoteness of archaeological and tourist places from means of transportation.
- 3- While the most prominent challenges facing sustainable tourism development in Matrouh Governorate are as follows: accumulation of tourism activity in specific periods (summer season), which leads to higher prices and tourism services and sudden pressure on facilities, and archaeological and tourist places are far from means of transportation and seasonality of tourism work The low level of training for workers in the tourism sector, in addition to the high prices of entering beaches, the high prices of gasoline and petroleum derivatives, the high prices of tourism and hotel goods and services, the behavior of citizens with tourists and their financial exploitation, and the lack of potable water in some areas, in addition to the lack of facilities and services in tourist attractions and conflicting laws. Added to that, legislation related to tourism work between the various institutions and bodies. We conclude from the above that there is a difference and diversity of challenges facing sustainable tourism development in the Alexandria region with its three governorates, depending on the nature of each governorate.
- 4- This represents the answer to the first and main question of the study. Thus, the first objective of the study has also been achieved, which is to identify the most important challenges facing sustainable tourism development in the Alexandria region.
- 5- The study also found that workers in the private tourism sector depend on Alexandria Radio as a main source for identifying the challenges of sustainable development in the Alexandria region, more than workers in the government sector, while less than half of the sample depend on average on local media as a main source for the challenges of sustainable development. In the Alexandria region, while the aspects of benefit were represented in knowing the challenges of sustainable tourism development in the Alexandria region and knowing the efforts of the state and various institutions in the field of sustainable tourism development, in addition to knowing the laws and regulations related to increasing the rates of sustainable tourism development and how to preserve the environment and identify obstacles to tourism development. Most of the reasons for not benefiting from following tourism and environmental programs on Alexandria Radio are due to the fact that they are not presented in an attractive manner and lack immediacy, and are very late in addressing the challenges of sustainable tourism development and do not address them in a timely manner and illustrative examples of the tourist and environmental information it provides.

With these results, the second question, and the second objective of the study was also achieved.

One of the findings of the study is that less than half of the respondents working in the tourism sector (governmental and private) sometimes watch Alexandria Radio, and less than half of the respondents working

in the tourism sector (governmental and private) sometimes watch Alexandria Radio. While less than a third of the respondents follow Radio Alexandria. The rate of listening to Alexandria Radio is higher among workers in the private tourism sector than in the government sector.

The study also found that most of the periods in which the sample members of the tourism sector (governmental and private) follow the programs presented through the radio station in Alexandria are the evening period between 5 pm - 10 pm, and the evening period after 10 pm

This represents the answer to the third question of the study, while the media treatment of the challenges facing sustainable tourism development through Alexandria Radio from the perspective of workers in the tourism sector is to host specialists and officials in the field of tourism, and to provide programs aimed at identifying these problems and obstacles and providing solutions to those challenges.) in its media treatment, and thus the third objective of the study has been achieved.

The study also concluded that among the proposals of workers in the tourism sector to activate the role of (Alexandria Radio) in serving sustainable tourism development issues, represented in increasing the participation of specialists in presenting sustainable tourism development issues for their ability to convince more of the challenges and problems of tourism development, in addition to addressing challenges that face the local sustainable tourism development and providing solutions to it, in addition to the interest of programs and media materials in the issues of sustainable environmental tourism development in addition to presenting tourism materials in periods that enjoy higher listening rates, and these were the proposals of workers in the tourism sector.

Agreement and Disagreement with T\the Results of Previous Studies:

1- As agreed with the study of (Ruiz, 2017) (Hakim, 2016) (Ghobadi, Gholam reza Janbaz., and Verdian, Mahin Shah, 2016) that there are multiple and diverse challenges facing sustainable tourism development in general, as agreed with the study (Abdel-Rasoul, 2016) that there are many challenges facing sustainable tourism development in Egypt, as agreed with the study of (Muhammad Ibrahim Iraqi, Farouk Abd al-Nabi Atallah, 2007)

That there are a set of obstacles towards the application of sustainability in the basic elements of the environment in Alexandria Governorate.

I agree with (Iman Al-Alami and Abboud Zarqin, 2016) where you are the media plays a positive role in helping to achieve sustainable development plans and goals. The current study proved that identifying and knowing the challenges facing sustainable tourism development helps the success of development plans in the region.

The difference with the study (Ghobadi, Gholam reza Janbaz., and Verdian, Mahin Shah, 2016) is that prosperity of tourism in each geographical area is linked to air, water, sound pollution, waste accumulation and environmental pollution, as the study proved that the challenges facing tourism development vary according to the governorate and its geographical nature.

Theoretical Implications of the Results:

Through the previous presentation of the most important findings of the current study, and in comparison with the theory of dependence on the media, we can say that it is the realization of the basic hypothesis of the theory that says that the public's dependence on the media increases whenever the media system is able to respond to the public's needs, and this is confirmed by the results of the study, which are:

The higher rate of benefit among workers in the private tourism sector from their follow-up to programs related to tourism and the environment provided by (the radio) than workers in the government tourism sector, which indicates that (the radio) was the closest in following up on these challenges in its local community.

Affected hypothesis the extent to which individuals depend on the media varies in several variables, the most important of which are: the nature of the media in society and the extent of their diversity and multiplicity, and the content they provide, in addition to the factors specific to the community itself, and this was confirmed by the results of the study in terms of the different degree of dependence on the part of workers in the tourism sector (governmental and private), and between their presence in the private societies of each of the governorates province the study.

Recommendations and Suggestions for the Study:

Based on our previous discussion of the results of the study, the researcher presents a set of recommendations aimed at developing some aspects of performance and professional practice in the field of local media, as follows:

- 1- Establishing a research unit in Alexandria Radio to follow up the challenges of sustainable tourism development.
- 2- The need to strengthen the transmission and terrestrial and satellite broadcasts for each of the regional radio stations and channels, and to provide external radio units and to go out to the tourist places in the region.
- 3- Creating a special website for regional channels and radio stations on the Internet, through which: Providing live broadcasts for local channels and radio stations, creating an electronic archive of all broadcast programs and episodes, to allow more listening and viewing opportunities of communication with the target audience.
- 4- Searching for funding sources and increasing the budget of local channels and radio stations to suit the media product, and providing transportation and accommodation for work teams to assist in the rapid, immediate and distinguished media coverage of the event.

To Improve Optimal Employment Opportunities for Media Coverage of Sustainable Tourism Development Issues and Challenges. the Researcher Suggests the Following:

- 1- Unifying the effort in terms of providing media professionals (with information, studies, analyzes, and successful and similar experiences) so that media can develop the means of producing development programs. Therefore, cooperation between the National Media Authority and research centers is necessary to provide studies on the real needs of the public.
- 2- Conclusion of more cooperation agreements between the National Media Authority, tourism institutions and bodies, and the Ministries of Antiquities, Tourism and Environment, and the need to provide scientific training to develop the capacities of (broadcasters, presenters and directors).
- 3- The researcher recommends that the contact person should adhere to impartiality, while covering the various tourism challenges, in addition to Increasing the hosting of specialists, for their ability to convince more of the challenges and problems of tourism development, in addition to presenting tourism radio materials in the periods that have the highest rates of listening and viewing. It was the different period that discusses those challenges more.

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